

SHORT NOTES

Preparation of some Optically Active 5-Substituted Rhodanines as Potential Anticonvulsants

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2-Mercapto-4-thiazolidones or Rhodanines possess insecticidal and fungicidal properties¹. The rhodanines when alkylated in 5-position show pharmacological properties similar to barbituric acid derivatives.²⁻³

Optically active 3-aryl-5-(2-methylbutyl)-2-mercapto-4-thiazolidones of the type (I) have been prepared from different substituted aryl groups from amines like aniline, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-, toluidines, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-anisidines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines, and *p*-phenetidine by converting them into their respective ammonium dithiocarbamates and condensing with (+)- α -bromo- α -(2-methylbutyl)-acetic acid:

(Where R = Me, OMe, Cl, and OEt)

Campbell and McKail⁶ have shown that the excess of ammonia favours the formation of tri-thiocarbamate, whereas more than molar proportion of carbon disulphide increases the yield of dithiocarbamates.

The optically active rhodanines of type (I) have been prepared and their optical rotations measured (Table I).

1. Bashour, *Chem. Abst.*, 1956, 50, 11598.
2. Erlenmeyer, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1938, 21, 11.
3. Doran and Shonle, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, 3, 193.
4. Badsher *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 384.
5. Brown *et al.*, *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, 59, 592.
6. Campbell and McKail, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1251.

TABLE I

No.	R	M.P.	Specific Rotation [α] _D ²⁵	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	Phenyl	65°	+4.976	5.83	5.01	22.67	22.94
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	96°	+1.431	4.52	4.77	21.59	21.84
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	153°	+5.183	4.41	4.77	21.60	21.84
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	181°	+3.066	4.20	4.46	20.29	20.42
5.	<i>m</i> - "	117°	-1.210	4.12	4.46	20.18	20.42
6.	<i>p</i> - "	88°	+13.17	4.12	4.46	20.16	20.42
7.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	80°	+2.225	4.08	4.33	19.67	19.82
8.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	97°	+9.568	4.27	4.53	20.39	20.71
9.	<i>m</i> - "	102°	+4.506	4.24	4.53	20.29	20.71
10.	<i>p</i> - "	84°	+1.640	4.25	4.53	20.30	20.71
11.	2,3-dichlorophenyl	124°	+1.936	3.83	4.02	18.27	18.40

It has been found that when the substituent in aromatic part is Me as in case of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluidines, the *p*-compound has more optical rotation than the *o*-compound; in case of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-chloroanilines, the *p*-compound has the highest optical rotation and *o*-has the least; but in case of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-anisidines, the *p*- has the least rotation and *o*- has the highest.

(+)- α -Bromo- α -(2-methylbutyl)-acetic Acid.—To a hot solution of potassium hydroxide (200 g. in 200 ml of water) was added (+) 2-methylbutylmalonic acid ester (230 g.) [prepared by the interaction of (+)1-bromo-2-methylbutane, α_D^{25} (+) 1.074 (102 g.) with malonic ester (117 g.) in presence of sodium ethoxide prepared from 19.6 g. sodium and 350 ml. of absolute alcohol] during 60 min. The potassium salt was cooled and acidified with HCl (conc.). The aqueous layer was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract separated, dried, and treated with bromine (160 g.) over a period of 2 hr. The contents were kept open for several days and then decarboxylated by heating in an oil bath at 120° to 135° for 4 hr, providing the desired acid, b.p. 130-35°/15-20 mm., yield 124 g. (60%), [α]_D²⁵+ 1.032. (Found: C, 40.62; H, 5.93; Br, 37.62. C₇H₁₃Br O₂ requires C, 40.20; H, 6.22; Br, 38.28%).

The dithiocarbamates from different substituted aromatic amines were prepared according to the method of Holmberg⁷.

Optically active 3-aryl-5-(2'-methylbutyl)-2-mercapto-4-thiazolidones were prepared^{8,9}

7. Holmberg, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3068.

8. Julian and Strugis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1126.

9. Nicolet and Bait, *ibid.*, 1927, 49, 2064.

by using the following procedure:

Anhydrous sodium carbonate was added till basic to (+)- α -bromo- α -(2-methylbutyl)-acetic acid (0.05M), dissolved in 40% NaOH solution (5 ml). To this, ammonium dithiocarbamate, prepared as above, was added at 5-10° during 20 min. with constant stirring. HCl (conc., 17 ml) was added and the mixture heated on a water bath at 85-90° for 30 min. The yellow oil separating was solidified on keeping in a refrigerator for several days. The solidified product was crystallised from ethanol. Specific rotations of these rhodanines were taken in acetone.

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